

**A RESEARCH PROPOSAL ON OIL SEED PRODUCTION, VALUE
CHAIN ANALYSIS AND BENEFITS THAT ACCRUE THE PRIMERY
PRODUCER .IN AFAR REGIN, ETHIOPIA**

**A Research Proposal in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements for Degree of
Master
of Arts on oil seed production, value chain analysis and benefits that accrue
the primary producer .in afar region, Ethiopia**

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Jan, 2015

Semera, Ethiopia

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ABBREVIATIONS

AMC	Agricultural Marketing Corporation
BDS	Business Development Services
CSA	Central Statistics Authority
EEPA	Ethiopian Export Promotion Agency
GCC	Global Commodity Chain
GVC	Global Value Chain
ISO	International Standard Organization
MIS	Market Information System
NGO	Non-governmental Organization
SPSS	Statistical Package for Social Science
USD	United States Dollar

1. CHAPTER ONE INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background to the Study

Ethiopia's export relies heavily on selected agricultural commodities originating mainly from smallholder peasant farming. Coffee, hides and skins, chat and oilseeds are the most important export items in the order of priority. Oilseeds contribute about 8.8% of the total export in 2002 with a growing share in export earning and volume over the last few years. Oilseeds is not only an export item. There is also large demand for it in the domestic economy since it is used to produce edible oil and oilcake. The total earning from the oilseeds business, particularly from the export market, has increased over the past few years. However, the gain from the business is not fairly distributed and does not properly reach to the primary producers who find themselves at the end of an extended market chain. The primary producers have no proper access to the final market and lacked knowledge on how to add value through partially or fully processing the oilseed products before it is supplied to the market. This has been a cause for substantial income loss of the majority of farmers.

The main grain items categorized as oilseeds are 'noug seed' (*Guizotia Abyssinia* also known as Niger seed), linseed, rapeseed, sesame seed, sunflower seed, and groundnuts. The Ethiopian Export Promotion Agency (EEPA) followed other classification. According to the latter classification cottonseed, castor oilseeds, mustard seeds, safflower seed, and oleaginous fruit are also included in the oilseeds category. The major items in the order of importance in 2002 export data of the EEPA are sesame seed, oilseeds and oleaginous fruit, groundnuts, mustard seed, castor seed, cotton seed, rapeseed and linseed.

According to information collected from oilseeds exporters in Addis Ababa, noug seed is the second most important export item. However, it is categorized as 'oilseeds and oleaginous fruit' in the EEPA classification for unexplained reason. This indicates that there is no standard classification procedure for oilseeds by government institutions and there is also lack of consistency in recording and keeping the flow of all export commodities.

Sesame seed is the most important export commodity item. It contributes for nearly 80% of the total share of oilseeds export in 2002. While other oilseeds together contribute for only 20% of the total export.

grain market structure created unfair market interaction between the government parastatal and farmers by setting official prices below producers cost. According to Amha (1994) estimation, the magnitude of producer's losses varied from 24 to 52% in two major grain products of maize and teff⁸⁷ respectively.⁸⁸ this implies that oilseeds producers were also affected by the policy and experienced a certain magnitude of producers' loss. According to the World Bank research, oilseeds played a key role in Ethiopia's export in the early 1970s, just before the reform. For instance, in 1974/75, about 79,000 tons of oilseeds were exported. The volume of export declined to 6,000 tons in 1978/79. This was primarily because the peasants gave first priority to growing basic cereal staples after the market reform in order to meet their basic food needs as their income had been highly deteriorated.

Donors and international lenders criticized the regulated agricultural market regime pursued by the government and put condition for a loan to be effected to the country.⁹⁰ Due to this intensified pressure, the government enacted an abrupt and sudden market reform overnight in 1990. The following quotation is taken from the proclamation of March 1990.

“In the trade sector of the economy, the private entrepreneurs will be able to compete with state run enterprise and agriculture or industrial commodities as well as in import export trade. In the area of trade in grain products in particular, trade exchange will henceforth be conducted on the basis of free market pricing while the control situation and the quota system cease. The AMC will enter free market and operate as a state trade organization”.

Soon after the reform, the private sector entered into inter regional and export trade with a relatively minor regulatory controls pertaining to external trade and licensing. Despite the reform, however, Ethiopia's oilseeds export further declined in 1991/92 to just 176 tons due to the disruption of civil war in the country. No significant recovery was registered in 1992/93

Regarding afar regional state have a potential of oil seed production where by their environmental suitability concern. This opportunity for producer of oil seed has great chance for compete in exportation. In afar region there is suitable environment for production of oil seed. Primery producer can able to earn big benefit from it by connect with global net work. Afar value chain theoretical framework is helpful in the analysis because it is a descriptive construct, which could be used to generate and analyze data on how to make better income from the networks of both national and international markets.

Hence, the primary agenda of this research is the assessment of the possibilities for smallholder farmers to secure a reasonable share of benefit from the value added chain of the oilseeds business.

This proposal intends to answer the following research question – “*Does value addition at oilseed production and/or spreading the gain from export of oilseed products increase the income of the primary producers?*” This proposal concerns theoretical framework of the global value chain analysis to inform the debate on how the oilseeds sub-sector could be better utilized to enable the primary producers to earn better income.

1.2. Problem Statement

Even though the country has thirty million hectares of potential oil seed production area, the amount of arable land under oil seed cultivation during 2009 (185,000ha) is very small as compared to the potential (MoARD, 2010). Beside, inefficient utilization of oil seed production area, the same author illustrated that input supply, agronomic practices, pre and post harvest handling, marketing, utilization and overall investment are some of research and development gaps and priorities under the current situation of oil seed production in Ethiopia. Organizations that are working on oil seed development, however, mainly focus on adaptation and release of locally adapted varieties. They do not give importance to the other activities (input supply, post harvest processing, marketing and utilization) across the value chain. Federal and Regional research centers are concentrating on the evaluation and release of new varieties for local producers.

However, to increase production and productivity and to get competitive advantage from the development of oil seed sector, there should be innovation at every stage of the value chain. Bammann (2007) illustrated that the value chain concept helps to trace product flows; show value addition at different stages; identify key actors and their relationships in the chain; identify enterprises that contribute to production, services and required institutional support; identify bottlenecks preventing progress; provide a framework for sector-specific action; identifies strategy to help local enterprises to compete and to improve earning opportunities and identify relevant stakeholders for program planning. Recently, the demand for production and

consumption of oil seed varieties is increasing tremendously by farmers in the study area (*afar*) as well as neighboring Districts' like; *zone1 & zone3*. The main factors for the existing demand are availability of land with conducive soil characteristics for oil seed production and climatic condition, search for alternative cereal crop for consumption, crop rotation and diversification, and need of crop residue for livestock fodder.

According to IPMS (2005), soils in the area where about a quarter of the size of the District is Haplic Luvisols soils and about 22% are Vertisols or soils with vertic properties. Many of the areas are also flat. Hence, seasonal water logging, especially during the heavy rainfall months, is so high and it is the main production problem in the study area. Such a condition is not conducive for the dominant commercial crops (sesame and **cotton**) production in the area. Household income and food security of rural farmers could be affected by the decline in the production of such crops due to the water logging problem. Besides, such a problem also lead to natural resources degradation especially of forests. This is because farmers' clear forest areas in search of farm land to compensate the amount of land abandoned due to water logging. On the contrary, oil seed has potential to grow in water logging conditions. There is also need for alternative cereal crop in *afar*.

Sorghum is the only cereal that can be used for household consumption and crop rotation. Considering such huge demand and potential agro-ecology; various research, development and none governmental organizations put some effort to introduce and raise oil seed production in the area. Yet, farmers are still facing different problems like, input supply (improved seed and fertilizer), post harvest handling (particularly of shortage of oil seed polisher and thresher), and lack of market information for the seed as well as grain, and its utilization. Therefore, this entails a need for more comprehensive study which rigorously examine the oil seed value chain in the study area. oil seed is a new and only recently introduced crop and lacks in-depth studies. Accordingly, very few studies have been done on oil seed (Getachew,2000; Biruhalem and Dessalegn, 2007 and MoARD, 2010). However, most of these studies have focused on production (adaptation trials) or they are simple informal surveys. Rather there is no comprehensive study made so far to understand the whole oil seed value chain in the study area, *afar*. This is the first study of its kind which analyzes the entire value chain from input supplier

to the consumer. This study has the benefit of an integrated/holistic approach that tries to analyze the dynamics of input supply, production, marketing, post harvest processing and consumption of oil seed in the study area. Through such an approach, potential areas or entry points can be identified for infusing further innovation to upgrade the value chain. It also provides a holistic picture of existing challenges and opportunities in the oil seed value chain, allowing identifying and taking appropriate intervention measures for improvement. To understand opportunities and constraints in addressing the existing problems and to increase competitive advantage of the oil seed production in the area, this study was designed to achieve the following specific objectives.

1.3. Objectives of study

1.3.1 General Objective

- To identify challenges and opportunities for innovation along the oilseed: sesame production and its value chain in Afar regional state, Ethiopia.

1.3.2 Specific Objectives

- To identify the actors/stakeholders and assess their roles/ functions, linkages, attitude, habits and practices in the sesame value chain
- To analyze the institutional arrangements and enabling environment that affect the functioning of the sesame value chain
- To identify and analyze recent innovation activities related to development along the sesame value chain and assess their immediate outcomes

1.4. Research Questions or Hypotheses

- Who are the actors/stakeholders involved in the sesame value chain? And what are their characteristics, functions/roles, linkages, attitude, habits and practices?

- What institutional arrangements and enabling environments are affecting the functioning of the sesame value chain?
- What recent innovation activities are undertaken in development of the sesame value chain and what outcomes are obtained?
- What challenges, opportunities and entry points are available for infusing further innovation (technological, institutional and organizational) for upgrading the sesame value chain?
- What short-term actions/interventions should be taken to pursue opportunities and address constraints?

1.5. Significance of study

The study will generate valuable information on oilseed value chain that will assist Afar agricultural research centre for better intervention through the identified research gaps to change the livelihood of households. The study analyzes the entire oil seed value chain from input supplier to the consumer. It also provides a holistic picture of existing challenges, opportunities and entry points in the oil seed value chain. Therefore, it can shed light on required efforts to enhance the production and utilization of the crop at larger scale to ensure food security and self-sufficiency and bring about economic development in the area. The information generated will also help a number of organizations; research and development organizations, traders, producers, policy makers, extension service providers, NGOs, to assess their activities and redesign their mode of operations and ultimately influence the design and implementation of policies and strategies. It can also help such actors and others to identify and analyze new ways of stimulating innovation.

1.6 Scope of the Study

The study will cover under oil seed classification the so called sesame production found in Afar regional state. The study also encompasses sesame value chain analysis in the study area.

2. CHAPTER TWO LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Review of basic value chain

There is no clear indication in the literature as to when and who used the value chain approach for the first time. Girvan (1987) argues that analysts charting a path of development for mineral exporting economies used the concept of the value chain in the 1960s and 1970s. French researchers adopted the concept and used it as an analytical tool for empirical agricultural research. The French agricultural commodity chain research is known as *filiere* study and has its origin in technocratic agricultural research. The *filiere* study was mainly restricted to agricultural commodities in developing countries and was heavily influenced by the colonial and postcolonial economic policy of French. This is attributed to the fact that the agricultural development policy of the French colonies was commodity centered.

The concept of the value chain enters into the mainstream thinking after the groundbreaking work of Michael Porter in 1979. The goal of Porter's theory is to find a useful framework for understanding the essence of competition and narrows the gap between theory and practice. In his 1990 work, Porter addresses a question why some nations succeed and others fail in the international market. To answer this question, Porter traces back to the theories of absolute and comparative advantage of nations of Adam Smith and David Ricardo respectively. Porter argues that the pattern of nation's export and import explained by these traditional theories have limitations to inform today's international trade as the nature and scope of competition has changed. Porter identifies two key constructs that are necessary for the upgrading of firms competitiveness. The first is referred to as the *value chain*, which disaggregates the firm into its strategically relevant activities.

The second theoretical construct is the concept of the *value system*, which explains a large stream of activities between forwardly and backwardly linked firms. Porter's value chain framework could be applied to decompose a single firm into strategically important activities and to the understanding of its impact on cost and value. Porter (1985, 1990) argues that the overall value chain logic and its corresponding idea of securing a competitive advantage through applying generic strategies is applicable to all firms within an industry. His idea of the value chain is designed primarily as a heuristic tool to allow to individual firms or countries to understand which in-house (firm level

activities) and external steps can effectively improve their competitiveness. It helps to design a strategy that could generate the highest value addition through adoption of the most effective competitive strategies. The main limitation of Porter's value chain construct, however, is its weakness to look into the full range of activities, including *coordination*, that are required to bring a specific product from its conception to end use and beyond. Another construct that evolves in the value chain theory is the concept of the Global Commodity Chain (GCC). The notion of a commodity chain, as 'a network of labour and production processes whose end result is a finished commodity' comes from Hopkins and Wallerstein (1986, 1994).

The theory of the GCC is used to discuss the nature of international chains for agricultural products that are involved in the commodity chains either as producers of inputs to others or user of inputs from others. The GCC approach started to attract wide attention of researchers in the mid 1990s. The GCC theoretical approach, which was first centered on the study of agricultural commodity chain, later started to be used for a value chain research of other commodities beyond agriculture. Gereffi, Humphrey and Sturgeon (2003) argue that the theory will help third world country policy makers to assess the situation of global market structure and devise a policy programme that support firms of these countries to be able to enhance their position in the global market.

Gereffi, Humphrey and Sturgeon (2005) argue that power relation within the global value chain determines the market share and the income distribution that arises from the market. Another much cited writer on the value chain theory is Raphael Kaplinsky. Kaplinsky's work is focused on finding a sound link between the theory and practical research undertakings of the GVC. He develops a methodology to conduct a research on how the gains from globalisation can be spread to poor countries and poor people using the GVC theoretical approach. In 2000, Kaplinsky (in collaboration with Mike Morris) developed a 'value chain research manual', which can be used by academic writers and practitioners. A host of other writers added to the GVC theory and conducted a number of empirical researches using the theory

2.2. Limitations, weaknesses and research gaps

The basic literature reviewed in the previous section has its own weaknesses and limitations. Porter is concerned with the question how firms and countries could be competitive in the local and

international markets. His approach doesn't look at the whole value chain of a product from production to end-use. Moreover, it ignores the coordination of activities that are divided among firms and that have a global nature. This proposal is basically looking on how the market structure look like, who are the participants, where is the big return available and what should be done to upgrade the income of farmers. As a result, Porter's value chain approach will not be useful for this proposal because it will doesn't look into the relationship of upper and lower tire firms within the chain and will not explore the possibilities for upgrading which arises from this relationship. Although significant achievement has been made in theorizing GVC since the beginning of the 1990s, more remains to be achieved. In this theoretical approach the process of coordination and competition among actors operating in the same function have been given less attention. Furthermore, the analysis focuses on more explicit structural elements of production, distribution and conception than on the social/cultural/ and symbolic relations among actors. Hence, efforts and further debates are still needed to clarify the key concepts of the GVC theory. In spite of the above weaknesses, the GVC is concerned with how poor countries and firms from these countries could benefit more from globalisation and global income distribution. The theory gives a practical tool for devising a strategy for upgrading and conducting empirical research in the field. The approach can help strategy makers of the third world countries to determine where the highest value can be captured within the national component of the GVC. It also helps to identify the main governing bodies of the chain and the rule setting and monitoring procedures of the governors. This theoretical approach helps firm managers and policy makers from third world countries to better understand the rules and regulation of the governing bodies of buying companies and to be able to command a better share through upgrading of product types and responses to the different market needs. In general, the approach can be used for practical research purposes in the following ways:

- Mapping out the chains and identifying actors involved in particular production sectors: i.e. identifying the different types of activity, geographical location and actors involved in different roles at different levels,
- Following up the relative distribution of 'values ' and the reasons for inequalities and/or inefficiencies and blockages in the chain, and
- Based on the above two analysis: identifying the potential 'leverage' points for upgrading in the chain as a whole and/or redistributing values in favour of those at the bottom.

Although the GVC approach was initially used for the purposes mentioned above, the approach is now being adopted and used for a research topic intended to promote poverty oriented enterprise development within a national boundary of a country. For example, the approach can be used to identify the issues where financial services are particularly appropriate or inappropriate for micro finance programmes and credit and saving groups. It can also be used in business development services (BDS) to identify the level at which services might need to be integrated. In the same vein, the approach would be relevant for the oilseeds value chain because it could help to investigate how the income of oilseeds farmers could be increased through upgrading measures within the components of the value chain.

Based on the framework above, this research is intended to investigate oilseeds issues in two areas of the value chain nodes. The first one is investigation of the value chain network between farmers to exporters (including investigation of what is required in the export market) and the second one is looking for possibilities of upgrading in local processing of oilseeds by farmers (farmer organization). The theory could be applied to a practical research work through drawing a value chain diagram and identifying the main market players, through calculating the value addition and income share of different market players, through assessing the governance structure of the chain and through identifying areas where upgrading is possible within the chain.

2.3. Relevance of the global value chain theory

Kaplinsky and Morris (2000) develop a comprehensive global value chain research manual, based on the theoretical framework of the GVC approach. The manual is prepared in such a way that it allows researchers to get deep in and utilize what is relevant and appropriate in the investigation of the value chain. The manual gives a range of tools that are deemed suitable to the research question as each chain has its own peculiar characteristics.

3. CHAPTER TWO CONCEPTUAL FRAME WORK

3.1. What is global value chain?

In defining the concept of the value chain, different authors use different terminologies. Kaplinsky (2000) for example, uses the term value chain rather than global value chain. More recent literatures like Gibbon and Ponte (2005) use the term global value chain. A value added chain is the process by which technology is combined with labour, material and human knowledge and then processed inputs are assembled, transported, marketed and distributed. A single firm may consist of only one link in this process or it may be extensively integrated vertically. In a more formal definition, the value chain describes the full range of activities, which are required to bring a product or service from conception, through the various phases of production (involving a combination of physical transformation and the input of various producers services), delivery to final buyers and final disposal after use. This value chain definition refers to a single product or service passing through the different phases from its conception to final use and disposal after use. Examples of such value chain is a cut flower produced in Ethiopia and passed through the different phases of design, production, purchase and use by a final user in Holland.

The general conceptualisation of the value chain can be explained by the following simple logic. Suppose a product is designed, produced and delivered to final users. This product is made of raw materials and other intermediate products. The raw materials and intermediate goods should be transported to the production facilities of the firm that produce the final product. In addition, the final product of the firm has to be transported to distribution centers and delivered to the final users. Final users will buy the product, use it and dispose the left over after use. The whole process of this design, production, marketing, use and final disposal of a certain product or service constitute the notion of a value chain. An example of a simple value chain as portrayed by Kaplinsky (2004) is presented in

Table 1: Simple value chain

Source: Kaplinsky, 2004, p. 80.

3.2. Value chain analysis as analytical tool for export promotion and development

Gereffi, Humphrey and Sturgeon (2005) discuss that the world economy has made a significant change in the past few decades especially in the area of international trade and free movement of capital. This historical trend has enhanced growth in the international trade and has facilitated conditions for the integration of the world economy. Globalization has provided opportunity for substantial income growth of countries, which started to participate in the global integration in recent years. This is reflected not only in high-income growth but also in the improved availability of better quality and differentiated products and services.

However, the circumstances under which globalization of trade and free movement of capital operate creates undesired income distributional pattern between people and countries. Such undesired global trade patterns, has widened the income gap and could be one factor for exacerbating the poverty situation in poor countries.

A case in point is the trade regime that is followed by the European Union (EU) and other industrialized nations in agricultural export to the regions. In 2001 for example, EU and other industrialized countries subsidy for their agricultural sector was amounted to United States Dollar (USD) 311 billion or about USD 850 million per day, dwarfed the amount those same countries gave to poor countries in the form of development assistance. This has created unfair competition between subsidized farmers of the industrialized nations and farmers of poor countries by creating a high entry barrier for export of agricultural products from poor nations to the developed countries market. As a result of this protectionism and subsidy, developing nations lose about USD 24 billion annually from agriculture or agro industrial income.⁵⁰ If we see it regionally, this same trade policy taxed about 10-15% of total agricultural and agro industrial income of Sub-Saharan African countries.⁵¹ This is a substantial sum for many poor Sub-Saharan African countries and would be a great obstacle to meet the millennium development goal.

The above factors could negatively affect the income share of developing countries, which are participating in the global trade. But, non-participation would be much daunting because through participation countries can still generate better income than distancing themselves from the global trade. But countries need to do it in a more systematic way so that they could get the maximum possible advantages/returns.

To this end, the global value chain approach could help to examine the different ways in which global production and distribution systems are functioning and help to devise possibilities for firms in developing countries to enhance their position in the global markets. The GVC approach could enable firms and policy makers in poor countries to analyze what is required in the global market. This can be done through: (1) mapping the value chain relations and tracing the point of entry to participate in the market, (2) assessing what is required in the international market, (3) identifying the main actors in the chain and how it is possible to meet their needs and requirements and (4) identifying the possibilities for upgrading (such as adding value through fully or partially processing the product before sell) in the chain.

4. CHAPTER FOUR METHODOLOGY

3.2 Research Design

In this study, mixed methods will be employed to get detail and diverse information on the same issue. Use of mixed methods also helps to triangulate the reliability of the information which will be gathered. It is usual for researchers to employ mixed method designs to investigate different aspects of the same phenomenon (Sarantakos, 1998). Both quantitative and qualitative methods will be employed. Semi-structured interview, focus group discussion, key informant interview and personal observation methods will be used to gather the required data. Cross sectional type of research design will be used.

3.2.1 Sampling Procedure

The study area, zone 1 & zone 2, is selected purposively since the area has high potential for oil seed production but is not efficiently utilized yet. Samples will be chosen from each segment of the chain to be included in this study using diverse sampling techniques. The two zones have 2 weredas and 3 kebeles. From each wereda will be selected purposively based on their accessibility and recent experience in oil seed production innovation. The farm households at the production stage of the value chain will be stratified into two zones; zone 1 & zone 3 have gender disaggregated data at least 15% female headed households were incorporated in the sample for this study. Finally sample of respondents will be selected using probability proportional to size method. Simple random sampling technique will be used to choose the ultimate sample of households. A total of 100 sample households were chosen for the study.

3.3.2 Study Area

The study will be conducted in Afar National Regional State (Gewané woreda). It is located 600 kms from Addis Ababa. The main ethnic group is Afar who are highly engaged in sedentary and nomadic way of life. The altitude of the area varies from 150 m below sea level to 1000 m above sea level. The minimum and the maximum annual temperature vary from 18 °C and 35 °C respectively. The region has

annual rain- fall (bimodal pattern) of 561 mm on the western edge of the escarpment and 225 mm on the lava plain and volcanic ash where only camels and goats are reared. The animal population in these region is composed of 700,000 cattle, 100,000 sheep, 2,000,000 goats, 16,000 donkeys and 300, 000 camels (ANRS).

3.3 Target Population

The population of the study consisted of zone 1&3 of people in urban and rural area in the in afar Regional state.

3.4 Sampling Techniques

Purposive and simple random sampling will employed as sampling techniques to select a total of 100 households, from oil seed producer, in the study area. An interview will conducted to collect the required information from a total of 100 respondents through semi-structured questionnaire survey and checklists.

3.4 Sample Size

The study population that will be sampled are traditionally managed small holders from different kebeles will be randomly selected using lottery system from , zone1 & zone 2, will selected purposively since the area has high potential for oil seed production but not efficiently utilized yet. Simple random sampling technique will used to choose the ultimate sample of households. A total of 100 sample households were chosen for the study. Total of 100 numbers of house hold from zone 1&3 will be registered. From each zone one wereda will be selected purposively Among each weredas 3 kebele will be sampled based on their accessibility and recent experience in oil seed production innovation. The farm households at the production stage of the value chain will stratified into two zone; zone1 & zone3. Finally sample of respondents will selected using probability proportional to size method.

3.5 Research Instruments

Both primary and secondary sources of data were used for the study. The secondary data include information that are obtained mainly from different reports, bulletins, websites and literatures, which are relevant to the theme of the study, were gathered from various sources to complement the survey-based analysis. The primary sources of data were questionnaires distributed to house hold

3.6 Data Collection Techniques

Both primary and secondary data will collect for the study. The secondary data were gathered from various sources including, NGOs who will involved in oil seed research and development activities in the study area. Besides, relevant literature, official reports and memos will also consult as secondary data source. Primary data will collected from sampled actors/stakeholders who will involved in input supply, production, marketing, post harvest processing, consumption and supportive services (research, extension, finance, and facilitation) along the oil seed value chain in Household survey, focus group discussion, key informant interview and personal observation methods will employed to gather the information required from such actors. Pre-tested interview schedule and checklists (topical guideline) will employed as survey instruments. Pretested Semi-structured interview schedule will used to collect data from farmers.

The interview schedule will pre tested on non-randomly selected households. Some modifications will made based on the result of the pretest. Interviewers, who know the area very well, will recruited and trained about the objectives of the study, methods of data collection and interviewing techniques and ethics, post harvest processing, consumption, as well as constraints/opportunities, enabling environment and potential interventions to remove the constraints and take advantage of the opportunities. Apart from farmers, primary cooperatives , farmers and some retailers who participated in oil seed marketing, grain millers as a post harvest processor, and supportive actors afar research centers, NGOs, District information office, and other administrative offices) will also interviewed to get a thorough understanding of all the

issues at all levels in the chain. Finally, very limited number of consumers in urban areas will also interview.

3.7. Data Analysis

Both qualitative and quantitative methods of data analysis will used. The study is largely qualitative in nature. System of thematic analysis was used for the data that will collected through focused group discussion, key informant interview, personal observation and secondary document analysis. Functional analysis will used to identify the various actors and their roles inthe value chain. Partnerships and linkages, which are central to innovative performance in value chain, will analyzed in their historical and contemporary context to understand their strengths and weaknesses. During analysis a number of tools will employed. For instance; chain mapping and actor linkage matrix were used to identify the various actors and their function, and for mapping patterns of interaction between actors. Actor time line will also used to identify recent innovation activities undertaken and their immediate outcome along the oil seed value chain in the study area.

Besides, SWOT (strength, weakness, opportunity and threat) analysis will used to analyze the challenges and opportunities for technological, institutional and organizational innovation across the value chain. Regarding the quantitative analysis, simple descriptive statistics such as simple measures of central tendency, mean, standard deviation, frequency, percentages and cross tabulation will used for the survey data gathered from sample farm households. Statistical package for social science (SPSS) version 17 will employed to analyze the data. The analyzed data are presented using tables, graphs and charts. Data collected through semi- structured questionnaire survey. The micro level data collected through self-administered interview is analyzed by using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) software. Close-ended questions are entered into the programme directly while open-ended questions will categorized, coded and entered into the database. Analyzed data from both sources are presented in the form of tables, graphs, and proportions. These output will used for interpretations and to support the writer's argument.

5. CHAPTER FIVE PROJECT COST

5.1. Logistics

Table 2. Cost of transportation in the field

Items/ activities	Unit	Unit cost (Birr)	Quantity	Total cost
Fuel	Liter	15.56	500	7780.00
Motor oil	5Liter	560	10	1120.00
Brake oil	Liter	150	3	450
Maintenance	Liter	10% of fuel		680
Contingency 10 %				863
<i>Total</i>				10893.00

Table 3. Per dime costs

Individuals	Daily allowance	Field days	Total cost
Rent vehicle	1750	35	61250
Personnel	185.4	35	6489
Two ass.	140.5	35	4917.5
Facilitator	50	35	1750
One driver	140.4	35	4917.5
Contingency 10 %			731.50
<i>Total</i>			80055.5

Table 4. Stationary materials, photocopying and Thesis binding costs

Item	Unit	Unit cost	Quantity	Total cost
Writing paper	Pack	80	4	320
Computer paper	Pack	120	4	480
Thin marker	Dose	85	2	170
CD WR	Psc	20	4	80
Flash disc	Psc	300	1	300
Record book	Psc	25	2	50
Writing pad	Psc	15	3	45
Photocopying	Pages	.25	600	150
Printing	Pages	1.00	300	300
Binding	Spiral size	12.00	10	120
<i>Total</i>				2015.00

Table 5. Summary of the project cost

Items	Total cost/Birr
Logistics	10893.00
Per dime cost	80055.5
Stationary cost	2015.00
Material cost	8,388.45
Total	101,351.95

5. PROJECT TIME TABLE

Table 6 : Time period break for different activities

Activities	January	February	March	April	May	June
Preparation of project proposal	x					
Questioner survey and Sample collection from study area		x				
Result analysis and Thesis writting			x			
Sending research to main advisor and co advisor for evaluation				x		
Progressing of thesis evaluation					X	
Thesis submission and preparation for defense						X

6. REFERENCES

- Porter, Michael (1985): *Competitive Advantage: Creating and Sustaining Superior Performance*. New York- London, The Free Press, Collier Macmillan Publishers
- Porter, Michael (1990): *The Competitive Advantage of Nations*. Hampshire-London, The Macmillan Press Ltd.
- Wolday, Amha (1995) “The Performance of Maize and Teff Marketing in Southern Ethiopia”.
In: Ethiopian Journal of Economics, Vol. 6, No. 1, April 1995, A Publication of the Ethiopian Economic Association, Addis Ababa University Printing Press, pp. 101-131.
- Gereffi, Gary and Sturgeon, Timothy (2004): *Globalization, Employment and Economic Development: A Briefing Paper*. Sloan Workshop Series in Industrial Studies, Rockport, Massachusetts, June 2004, <http://www.globalvaluechains.org> 07/04/2005.
- Gereffi, Gary; Humphrey, John and Sturgeon, Timothy (2003). “The Governance of Global Value Chains”: *Forthcoming, In: Review of International Political Economy*, November, 2003.
- Gereffi, Gary; Humphrey, John and Sturgeon, Timothy (2005). “The Governance of Global Value Chains”. *In: Review of International Political Economy*, Vol. 12, No. 11, February, 2005, Published by Routledge Taylor and Francis Group Ltd, pp. 78-104.
- Bammann, H. 2007. *Participatory Value Chain Analysis for Improved Farmer Incomes, Employment Opportunities and Food Security*. Pacific Economic Bulletin, Vol 22, No. 3, Apia..
- IPMS (improving productivity and market success) of Ethiopian farmers project. 2005. *Metema Pilot Learning Site Diagnosis and Program Design*. Available on.
<http://www.ipmsethiopia.org/Pilot-Learning-Sites/Metema.asp>. Accessed on March 2010
- CSA (Central Statistics Authority). 2003. *Statistical Report on Area and Production of Crops*. Part II-A. Addis Ababa, Ethiopia
- _____. 2007. Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia. Central Statistical Agency. *Agricultura Sample Survey 2006/2007*. Addis Ababa Ethiopia

- _____. 2008. *Agricultural Sample Survey 2008/09 (Sep.-Dec. 2008)*. Report on crop and livestock product utilization, volume VII, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia.
- Gibbon, Peter and Ponte, Stefano (2005) *Trading Down: Africa, Value Chains and the Global Economy*: Philadelphia, Temple University Press.
- Kaplinsky, Raphael (2000): *Spreading the Gains from Globalization: What Can Be Learned from Value-Chain Analysis?* Institute of Development Studies (IDS), IDS Working Paper 110.
- Kaplinsky, Raphael (2004): "Spreading the Gains from Globalization: What Can Be Learned from Value-Chain Analysis?" *In: Problems of Economic Transition*, Vol. 47, No. 2, Jun 2004, pp. 74-116.
- Kaplinsky, Raphael and Morris, Mike (2000): *A Handbook for Value Chain Research*. Birmingham, Prepared for IDRC, <http://www.globalvaluechains.org> 07/04/2005.
- MoARD (Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development). 2010. *National Rice Research and Development Strategy Of Ethiopia*. Addis Ababa, Ethiopia.
- Getachew Afework, 2000. *Rice Adaptation in Metema District North Gondar Zone of the Amhara Regional State*. Bureau of Agriculture, Bahir Dar. (Unpublished).
- Central Statistical Authority (2004) *Agricultural Sample Survey 2003/2004: Report on Area and Production of Crops, Private Peasant Holdings, Meher Season*, Vol. 1, 302 Statistical Bulletin, May 2004, Addis Ababa.
- Sarantakos, S. 1998. *Social Science Research*. 2nd edition, Macmillan Press Ltd, London